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Comparative Effects of Probiotic Kombucha Tea and Its Postbiotic-Like Cell-Free Filtrate on Metabolic Regulation in a Rat Model of Diet-Induced Obesity

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Abstract

This study aimed to examine the metabolic effects of probiotic kombucha tea and its postbiotic-like cell-free filtrate in a high-fat diet-induced rat model of obesity. Twenty-one male Wistar rats were rendered obese after four weeks of high-fat feeding and subsequently allocated to three groups (n = 7 per group): water control, probiotic kombucha, and kombucha-derived postbiotic. Interventions were administered orally at a dose of 4 mL/day for 60 days.

Core metabolic outcomes included body weight, adipose tissue distribution, serum lipid profile, liver enzyme activities (AST, ALT), oxidative stress (TBARS), and insulin resistance (HOMA-IR). Postbiotic supplementation resulted in a significant reduction in body weight ($p < 0.0001$) and circulating lipid parameters, including triglycerides, LDL, and total cholesterol. In addition, the postbiotic group exhibited increased brown adipose tissue mass ($p < 0.0001$) and improved HOMA-IR values, indicating enhanced insulin sensitivity. Oxidative stress levels were markedly reduced ($p < 0.0001$), whereas CRP concentrations remained unchanged.

Overall, kombucha-derived postbiotics exerted broader and more consistent metabolic effects than probiotic kombucha tea, particularly in relation to lipid metabolism, brown adipose tissue-associated parameters, and oxidative stress modulation.

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1. Introduction

The prevalence of obesity has been increasing globally, and it has emerged as one of the most persistent public health challenges worldwide. According to estimates from the

World Health Organization (WHO), the number of individuals affected by obesity is expected to exceed 230 million. National data from Turkey further support this trend, with the 2017 STEPS survey reporting that more than one-third of the adult population was living with obesity. Obesity is associated with a wide range of complications, including diabetes mellitus, cardiovascular disease, sleep apnea, respiratory disorders, osteoarthritis, and several types of cancer. Among metabolic comorbidities, non-alcoholic hepatic steatosis (NAHS) and insulin resistance are particularly prevalent, with NAHS currently recognized as the leading cause of liver disease in individuals with obesity [1–3].

Alterations in adipose tissue play a critical role in the development of obesity-related metabolic complications. As adipose depots expand, they become infiltrated by immune cells and exhibit increased secretion of pro-inflammatory cytokines such as tumor necrosis factor- α (TNF- α) and interleukin-6 (IL-6). These mediators impair insulin signaling and disrupt metabolic homeostasis [4]. Inflammatory processes are largely regulated through the nuclear factor kappa B (NF- κ B) and c-Jun N-terminal kinase (JNK) pathways, while dysregulated adipokine secretion and mitochondrial dysfunction further exacerbate systemic inflammation [4,5]. Given the multifactorial nature of these mechanisms, recent research has increasingly emphasized the need for multidisciplinary approaches, including the investigation of probiotics as potential modulators of obesity-related metabolic disturbances [6–9].

Obesity has been associated with alterations in gut microbiota composition, including an increased *Firmicutes/Bacteroidetes* ratio, which contributes to chronic low-grade inflammation and hepatic inflammatory cell migration [10]. These alterations may promote hepatocyte oxidative stress, apoptosis, and structural liver injury [11]. Beyond this phylum-level imbalance, obesity has also been linked to reductions in *Akkermansia muciniphila* and *Bacteroides spp.*, along with increases in the *Clostridium* and *Prevotella genera*, as well as members of the Ruminococcaceae and Lachnospiraceae families. Collectively, these microbial shifts are thought to influence energy harvest efficiency and intestinal permeability [12,13]. Biomarkers of liver injury, including alanine aminotransferase (ALT), alkaline phosphatase (ALP), bilirubin, aspartate aminotransferase (AST), gamma-glutamyl transferase (GGT), and lactate dehydrogenase (LDH), are commonly used to assess non-alcoholic hepatic steatosis (NAHS), with ALT considered a key indicator in individuals with overweight and obesity [14–16].

Considering the established interplay between gut microbiota and obesity, both probiotics and postbiotics have attracted attention as potential interventions for obesity-related metabolic disorders. In contrast to probiotics, postbiotics are characterised by greater stability and the direct delivery of bioactive microbial metabolites, without being compromised by gastrointestinal stress [17]. Fermented beverages such as kombucha have been shown to generate a diverse range of bioactive compounds during fermentation, suggesting potential metabolic regulatory effects. Several studies have reported that kombucha consumption may contribute to body weight reduction, alongside anti-inflammatory effects and improvements in dyslipidemia and glucose homeostasis [18]. However, comparative data evaluating the metabolic effects of probiotic kombucha tea versus its postbiotic-derived fractions remain limited.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Kombucha Tea Production and Postbiotics from Kombucha Tea

2.1.1 Kombucha tea production

The kombucha culture was obtained from Kombuçça (Istanbul, Turkey). The fermentation of Kombucha tea was carried out by modifying the fermentation method developed by Teoh et al. (2004) [19]. For fermentation, 20 g of black tea and 200 g of sugar beet powder were used in 2 L of distilled water, steeped with sugar for 10 min and then filtered. The strained sweetened tea was allowed to cool to room temperature, then transferred to a glass jar and the kombucha SCOBY culture was added. Approximately 10% (v/v) of the SCOBY starter culture was added to the fermentation. The fermentation was carried out at 25°C for 14 days, and at the end of the period the kombucha tea was obtained by straining. During the experiment (60 days), the fermentation of kombucha tea continued continuously and fresh tea was obtained.

2.1.2 Obtaining postbiotics from kombucha tea natural culture

To obtain postbiotics from fermented kombucha tea, the method of Humam et al. (2021) was modified and applied [20]. Kombucha tea was centrifuged at $9400 \times g$ for 20 min at 25 °C, and the supernatant was sterilized using 0.22 µm PTFE filters (MF-Millipore, Merck, Germany). The resulting postbiotic-like cell-free filtrate, containing microbial metabolites but devoid of viable cells, was stored at +4 °C and used in the experiments.

2.2. Descriptive Analysis of Kombucha Tea and Its Postbiotics

2.2.1 Lactic acid bacteria (LAB) population in kombucha tea

1 mL of kombucha tea was taken under aseptic conditions and homogenized in dilution liquid containing 0.1% peptone (Merck 107214) and 0.85% NaCl and further dilutions were performed in the same solution. De Man Rogosa Sharpe (MRS) agar (Merck1.10660) medium was used for the detection of LAB and incubated at 37°C for 72 hours [21]. LAB enumeration was performed in triplicate (three independent plating per sample dilution), and colony counts were expressed as mean ± SD.

2.2.2 Organic acid analysis of postbiotic

Organic acid analysis was performed only for postbiotic samples, which represent the stable bioactive fraction of kombucha. Organic acid determination in postbiotic samples was performed using UPLC-MS/MS device and based on the method of Dinçer et al. (2020) [22]. The samples were extracted with water:methanol (80:20) solution containing 0.1% formic acid and analyzed with the determined chromatographic parameters. Organic acid profiling was performed as a compositional characterization of the postbiotic filtrate

2.2.3 Bioactive properties of probiotic and postbiotic preparations

The bioactive properties of probiotic kombucha tea and its postbiotic preparation were evaluated in terms of total phenolic content and antioxidant capacity. Total phenolic content was determined using the Folin–Ciocalteu method, and results were expressed as gallic acid equivalents (mg GAE/mL). Antioxidant capacity was assessed using the DPPH radical scavenging assay following standard procedures. All measurements were performed in triplicate for each sample, and mean values were used to characterize the antioxidant potential of the fermented kombucha preparations and their cell-free postbiotic fraction [22]. Total phenolic content and DPPH radical scavenging capacity were measured in triplicate and reported as mean values.

2.2.4 Antimicrobial activity of kombucha-derived postbiotic

The antimicrobial activity of the kombucha-derived postbiotic was evaluated using disc diffusion, minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC), and time-kill assays, following modified standard methodologies [23–25]. All antimicrobial assays were performed in triplicate as independent experiments using freshly prepared bacterial cultures. Analyses

were conducted exclusively on the postbiotic preparation, as it represents the stable, cell-free fraction enriched with microbial metabolites.

The test microorganisms included *Salmonella enterica* ATCC 14028, *Escherichia coli* ATCC 25922, *Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC 25923, *Bacillus cereus* ATCC 11778, and *Listeria monocytogenes* ATCC 19118.

For the disc diffusion assay, bacterial cultures were grown for 18–24 h at 37 °C and adjusted to a 0.5 McFarland turbidity standard (approximately 1×10^8 CFU/mL). Sterile paper discs (6 mm diameter) impregnated with the postbiotic preparation were placed onto Mueller–Hinton Agar (MHA) plates previously inoculated with the test microorganisms. Plates were incubated at 37 °C for 24 h, and inhibition zones were measured in millimeters.

Minimum inhibitory concentrations were determined using the broth microdilution method in 96-well microplates. Serial dilutions of the postbiotic preparation were prepared in cation-adjusted Mueller–Hinton Broth (MHB) and inoculated with bacterial suspensions (1:100 dilution of a 0.5 McFarland standard). Plates were incubated at 37 °C for 12–18 h, and the lowest concentration showing no visible bacterial growth was recorded as the MIC.

Time-kill assays were conducted to evaluate bacteriostatic or bactericidal effects over time. Bacterial cultures were combined with the postbiotic preparation at a ratio of 1:100 (v/v) and incubated at 37 °C. Aliquots were collected at 0, 2, 4, 6, and 24 h, plated on MHA, and incubated for colony enumeration. Changes in viable cell counts were expressed as log CFU/mL using mean values derived from triplicate experiments.

2.3 Evaluation of Kombucha Tea and its Postbiotic Efficacy in Obesity

2.3.1 Experimental animal groups and experimental plan

The animal experiments were conducted at the Akdeniz University Centre for Experimental Animal Research and Application. Twenty-one male Wistar rats, eight weeks of age at the beginning of the study, were used. The animals were kept under standard environmental conditions (22 °C \pm 1 °C; 12-h light/12-h dark cycle) and monitored daily throughout the study.

All experimental procedures were approved by the Akdeniz University Local Ethics Committee for Experimental Animals (ID: 1678/2024.02.004) and carried out in accordance with international guidelines on the care and use of laboratory animals.

The high-fat diet (HFD) consisted of 35% vegetable oil (3.3% corn oil and 31.7% sunflower oil) and was supplied by Arden (Ankara, Türkiye). The diet was delivered with the cold chain maintained (4 °C) and followed the AIN-93M formulation, containing 20% casein, 25% corn starch, 15% sucrose, 5% cellulose, 2% mineral mix, 2% vitamin mix and 0.3% DL-methionine. Because all animals were intentionally rendered obese with this diet, a separate control-diet group was not included; the primary aim was to compare probiotic and postbiotic treatments under equal obese conditions.

The experimental design commenced with animals that had developed obesity. Twenty-one rats were fed the high-fat diet (HFD) for a period of one month, at which point a significant increase in body weight and adipose tissue accumulation was observed, thus confirming obesity. The rats were then randomly assigned to three groups (n = 7 each): The control group was administered water, while the Kombucha tea group received a probiotic formulation derived from Kombucha. The Kombucha-derived postbiotic group received a postbiotic preparation. The animals were housed individually in separate cages for a period of 60 days. This was done in order to prevent dominance stress and to ensure accurate monitoring of intake. The administration of treatments was conducted via oral gavage, with a volume of 4 mL allocated per day, administered in a single morning dose. The selected volume was based on preliminary tolerance trials and was delivered slowly using a rounded gavage needle according to institutional animal welfare

guidance. Rats were provided with unrestricted access to drinking water in a separate bottle throughout the study, and no indications of gastric distress or aspiration were observed.

2.3.2 Blood sampling and biochemical analysis

At the predetermined time points (days 0, 30, and 60), blood samples were collected from the tail vein by a veterinarian at Akdeniz University Animal Research Centre under standard anesthesia procedures. Serum samples were separated and transferred under cold-chain conditions to Tosun Laboratory (Antalya, Türkiye) for biochemical analysis. Lipid profile (HDL, LDL, triglycerides, total cholesterol), liver enzymes (AST, ALT), insulin, CRP, and lipase activity were quantified using validated automated analyzer protocols accredited by the Turkish Accreditation Agency (TÜRKAK). Rat body weights and blood glucose levels were recorded weekly throughout the experimental period.

2.3.3 Oxidative stress measurement in adipose and liver tissue (TBARS)

To evaluate the effect of obesity on adipose tissue distribution, epididymal white adipose tissue and liver samples were collected after euthanasia, weighed, and stored at -80°C until analysis. Oxidative stress levels were determined by the thiobarbituric acid reactive substances (TBARS) assay [26], and malondialdehyde (MDA) content ($\mu\text{mol MDA/kg}$) was quantified spectrophotometrically. The calibration curve was established using MDA standards, and the slope of the regression line ($y = 0.1425x + 0.1002$; $R^2 = 0.9975$) was used for calculations. TBARS measurements were performed in triplicate for each tissue homogenate sample, and values were expressed as mean \pm SD.

2.4 Statistical Analyses

Statistical analyses were performed using SPSS version 25.0 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY, USA) and GraphPad Prism version 9.0 (Dotmatics, San Diego, CA, USA). Data are presented as mean \pm standard deviation (SD). Prior to inferential analyses, the normality of data distribution and homogeneity of variances were assessed using residual histograms, the Shapiro–Wilk test, and Bartlett’s test, respectively.

Comparisons among experimental groups were conducted using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA), followed by Tukey’s post hoc test for multiple comparisons when appropriate. Pearson’s correlation analysis was applied to evaluate linear relationships between metabolic, biochemical, and adiposity-related variables. For visualization purposes, box-and-whisker plots were used to illustrate the distribution and variability of key parameters across groups.

All statistical tests were two-tailed, and a p-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

3. Results

3.1 Stabilization of Kombucha Culture and Characterization of Its Postbiotic

3.1.1 Antimicrobial Activity of Kombucha-Derived Postbiotic

The antimicrobial activity of the kombucha-derived postbiotic was evaluated against *Salmonella enterica* ATCC 14028, *Escherichia coli* ATCC 25922, *Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC 25923, *Bacillus cereus* ATCC 11778, and *Listeria monocytogenes* ATCC 19118 using disc diffusion, minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC), and time-kill assays.

The lowest MIC value was observed for *B. cereus* ($0.0038 \mu\text{L/mL}$), whereas the highest MIC was recorded for *E. coli* ATCC 25922 ($0.0153 \mu\text{L/mL}$). Intermediate MIC values ($0.0076 \mu\text{L/mL}$) were obtained for *S. aureus*, *S. enterica*, and *L. monocytogenes*.

Disc diffusion assays yielded inhibition zones of 12 ± 1 mm for *S. aureus* ATCC 25923, while *E. coli* ATCC 25922 and *L. monocytogenes* ATCC 19118 showed smaller zones (7 ± 1 mm). Overall, Gram-positive bacteria exhibited larger inhibition zones compared to Gram-negative strains.

Time-kill assays demonstrated a transient antimicrobial effect. A reduction in viable counts of *L. monocytogenes* ATCC 19118 was observed at 2 h, while both *L. monocytogenes* and *S. aureus* ATCC 25923 showed reduced viability at 4 h. Antimicrobial activity diminished by 6 h across all tested microorganisms, indicating a primarily bacteriostatic and short-lived effect.

3.1.2 Organic acid composition of postbiotic

The organic acid composition of the postbiotic was analysed, confirming the absence of propionic acid. The main organic acids detected were gluconic acid (1592.7 mg/kg), citric acid (372.8 mg/kg), oxalic acid (143.6 mg/kg), malic acid (1147.3 mg/kg), lactic acid (2383.4 mg/kg), acetic acid (8371.4 mg/kg) and succinic acid (30.5 mg/kg).

3.1.3 Stability analysis of kombucha tea culture

To assess the stability of the kombucha tea culture, titration analysis (an indicator of acidity), Brix analysis (an indicator of dissolved sugars) and color analysis were performed. These analyses were carried out on days 0 (start of fermentation), 2, 4, 8 and 14. The titration analysis showed an average acidity of 115.3 ± 66.11 g/L, with a minimum of 54.05 g/L and a maximum of 186.16 g/L. Brix analysis showed an average sugar content of 91.42 ± 0.3347 g/L, with a minimum of 91.2 g/L and a maximum of 92 g/L, confirming successful fermentation.

3.1.4 Antioxidant profile of kombucha tea and its postbiotic

The antioxidant properties of both kombucha tea culture and its postbiotic were assessed. The total phenolic content of kombucha tea was 34.86 mg/mL, while the postbiotic contained 31.14 mg/mL of total phenolic compounds. The antioxidant activity was determined to be 57.42 mg/mL for kombucha tea and 54.87 mg/mL for the postbiotic. These findings indicate that there is no significant difference in antioxidant activity between the kombucha tea and its postbiotic.

3.2 Evaluation of Metabolic and Biochemical Parameters in Experimental Groups

3.2.1 Body weight and adipose tissue distribution in experimental groups

The effects of kombucha tea and its postbiotic on body weight, adipose tissue, insulin sensitivity and liver function in a high-fat diet-induced rat model with obesity are shown in Figure 1 and Table 1. At baseline, there was no significant difference in body weight between groups ($p > 0.05$). However, throughout the experimental period, body weight increased in the control group (363.23 ± 37.38 g, min-max: 304.5–430 g), remained stable in the probiotic group (321.48 ± 16.99 g, min-max: 285–352 g) and decreased significantly in the postbiotic group (295.66 ± 47.70 g, min-max: 198–363 g, $p < 0.0001$) (Figure 1A).

Comparisons between groups showed that both the probiotic ($p < 0.0001$) and postbiotic ($p < 0.0001$) groups had significantly lower body weights than the control, although the difference between the kombucha tea and postbiotic groups was not statistically

significant ($p > 0.05$). White adipose tissue (WAT) weight was also significantly lower in the intervention groups compared to the control. The mean WAT weight was 10.53 ± 1.14 g (min-max: 9.0-12.2 g) in the control group, 7.34 ± 0.95 g (min-max: 6.2-9.1 g) in the probiotic group and 6.12 ± 2.13 g (min-max: 3.0-9.8 g) in the postbiotic kombucha group ($p = 0.0003$) (Figure 1B, Figure 1C). Further analysis revealed that the reduction in WAT weight was more pronounced in the postbiotic group compared to the probiotic group ($p = 0.0351$), although the difference between these two intervention groups was not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$). Quantitatively, BAT weight was markedly higher in the postbiotic group compared with the control group, reflecting the near absence of detectable BAT in obese control animals, while WAT weight was reduced by approximately 42%. These changes indicate a pronounced thermogenic and lipolytic response associated with postbiotic supplementation.

BAT weight, which plays a critical role in energy metabolism and thermogenesis, showed significant differences between the groups ($p < 0.0001$). No detectable brown adipose tissue was observed in the control group (0.0086 ± 0.012 g, min-max: 0-0.03 g), whereas it was significantly higher in the probiotic group (0.414 ± 0.090 g, min-max: 0.3-0.5 g) and the postbiotic group (0.714 ± 0.107 g, min-max: 0.5-0.8 g). Comparisons between groups showed that BAT weight was significantly higher in the postbiotic group compared to both the control ($p < 0.0001$) and probiotic groups, suggesting that postbiotic administration played a role in increasing brown adipose tissue and possibly enhancing thermogenesis.

3.3 Evaluation of Metabolic and Biochemical Parameters in Experimental Groups

Blood lipid profile, liver function and oxidative stress markers were analysed in detail. The observations were supported by statistical analysis of metabolic and biochemical changes between groups (Table 1) (Figure 1D-I). Significant changes were observed in the blood lipid profile. Triglyceride levels decreased significantly in the postbiotic group (126 ± 46.97 mg/dL) compared to the control group (186.8 ± 76.54 mg/dL, $p = 0.0013$). HDL levels increased in the postbiotic group (64.1 ± 19.78 mg/dL, $p = 0.0367$). LDL levels were significantly lower in the postbiotic group ($p = 0.0307$), while VLDL levels decreased in both intervention groups ($p = 0.0047$). Total cholesterol levels were significantly reduced in the probiotic (73.86 ± 12.48 mg/dL) and postbiotic (72.1 ± 19.37 mg/dL) groups compared to the control group ($p < 0.0001$). These results suggest a beneficial effect of postbiotics on lipid metabolism. Markers of liver function showed significant improvements. AST levels decreased in the probiotic (58.90 ± 3.506 U/L) and postbiotic (52.95 ± 3.84 U/L) groups compared to the control group (67.67 ± 8.2 U/L, $p < 0.0001$). ALT levels were significantly lower in the postbiotic group (38.38 ± 5.68 U/L) than in the control group ($p = 0.0048$) (Figure 1E, Figure 1F). Lipase levels were significantly increased in the postbiotic group ($p = 0.0053$) (Figure 1G). Liver weight was significantly reduced in the postbiotic group (9.04 ± 1 g) compared to the control group (12.67 ± 0.10 g, $p < 0.0001$), suggesting a protective effect on liver health.

Metabolic and inflammatory markers showed significant changes. HOMA-IR levels were reduced in both intervention groups compared to the control group ($p < 0.0001$) (Figure 1D), indicating improved insulin sensitivity. TBARS levels, a marker of oxidative stress, were significantly lower in the postbiotic group ($p < 0.0001$) (Figure 1I). However, CRP levels did not show a significant difference between groups ($p = 0.6062$), suggesting no marked anti-inflammatory effect.

3.4 Relationships between variables: correlation and regression analyses

Correlation analyses revealed clear associations between adiposity, lipid metabolism, oxidative stress, and insulin resistance parameters (Table 2, Figure 2). Body weight was negatively correlated with brown adipose tissue (BAT) mass ($r = -0.66$, $p = 0.001$) and HDL concentrations ($r = -0.47$, $p = 0.033$), while positive correlations were observed with white adipose tissue (WAT) mass, triglycerides, total cholesterol, HOMA-IR, liver enzymes (ALT and AST), and oxidative stress (TBARS) ($p < 0.05$).

Oxidative stress (TBARS) showed strong positive correlations with triglycerides ($r = 0.80$, $p < 0.0001$), total cholesterol ($r = 0.89$, $p < 0.0001$), and HOMA-IR ($r = 0.83$, $p < 0.0001$), and negative correlations with BAT mass ($r = -0.83$, $p < 0.0001$), lipase activity ($r = -0.76$, $p < 0.0001$), and HDL levels ($r = -0.77$, $p < 0.0001$).

Multiple linear regression analysis indicated that blood glucose and TBARS were independently associated with body weight gain ($R^2 = 0.92$, $p < 0.05$), whereas HOMA-IR and ALT did not remain significant predictors after adjustment. In a separate model, HDL showed an inverse association with oxidative stress, while body weight was positively associated with TBARS levels. No independent predictors were identified for BAT mass in the regression models, despite strong bivariate correlations.

3.5. Figures, Tables and Schemes

Figure 1. Effects of probiotic kombucha tea and its postbiotic on body weight, adipose tissue distribution, and metabolic parameters in diet-induced obese rats.

(A) Changes in body weight over the 60-day intervention period. Data were analyzed using two-way repeated-measures ANOVA followed by post hoc comparisons.

(B) Representative images of white adipose tissue (WAT) and brown adipose tissue (BAT) collected at the end of the experiment.

(C) Quantitative comparison of WAT and BAT weights between experimental groups.

(D) Homeostatic model assessment of insulin resistance (HOMA-IR).

(E) Serum aspartate aminotransferase (AST) levels.

(F) Serum alanine aminotransferase (ALT) levels.

(G) Serum lipase activity.

(H) Liver weight.

(I) Oxidative stress levels assessed by TBARS.

All values are presented as mean \pm SD ($n = 7$ per group). Single time-point variables were analyzed using one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's post hoc test. Statistical significance was accepted at $p < 0.05$

Figure 2. Correlation scatter plots illustrating the associations between oxidative stress (TBARS), adipose tissue parameters, and selected metabolic markers in rats with diet-induced obesity.

- (A) Brown adipose tissue (BAT) weight vs. TBARS.
- (B) White adipose tissue (WAT) weight vs. TBARS.
- (C) Lipase activity vs. TBARS.
- (D) BAT weight vs. Lipase activity.
- (E) BAT weight vs. HDL cholesterol.
- (F) BAT weight vs. HOMA-IR.
- (G) TBARS vs. Total cholesterol.
- (H) BAT weight vs. Triglyceride levels.
- (I) Lipase activity vs. WAT

Each point represents an individual animal (n = 21). Correlations were assessed using Pearson’s correlation analysis (see Table 2). Solid lines indicate linear regression fits, and dotted lines represent 95% confidence intervals. These correlations reflect associations between variables and do not imply causal relationships

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Table 1. Effects of probiotic kombucha tea and its postbiotic on body weight, adipose tissue distribution, lipid profile, liver enzymes, insulin resistance, oxidative stress, and inflammatory markers in diet-induced obese rats.

	Control Group		Kombucha tea Group		Postbiotic Group		<i>P value</i>
	$\bar{X}\pm SD$	Min-Max	$\bar{X}\pm SD$	Min-Max	$\bar{X}\pm SD$	Min-Max	
Triglyceride mg/dL	186.8±76.54	88-390	134.4±33.42	65-201	126±46.97	51-215	0.0013
HDL mg/dL	51.43±7.527	44-70	57.10±9.78	35-75	64.10±19.78	34-96	0.0367
LDL mg/dL	10.71±2.738	4.8-16.6	9.29±4.80	4.1-20.4	7.84±4.40	2.40-18.70	0.0307
VLDL mg/dL	37.35±15.31	17.6-78	26.89±6.684	13-40.2	25.22±9.393	10.2-43	0.0047
Total Cholesterol mg/dL	107.9±21.13	72-157	73.86±12.48	60-103	72.1±19.37	47-101	<0.0001
AST U/L	67.67±8.2	51-86	58.9±3.506	52-65	52.95±3.84	45-59	<0.0001
ALT U/L	46.62±9.516	32-71	40.57±4.643	31-47	38.38±5.679	30-51	0.0048
Lipase U/L	4.22±0.42	3.4-4.7	4.48±0.66	3.3-5.1	4.78±0.87	3-6	0.0053
Liver Weight g	12.67±0.10	11.7-14.4	10.93±0.47	10.1-11.5	9.043±1.00	3.4-11.4	<0.0001
HOMA-IR (dimensionless index)	0.08±0.01	0.06-0.10	0.06±0.02	0.03-0.08	0.053±0.01	0.04-0.08	<0.0001
TBARS							
Oxidative stress nmol/g	0.029±0.01	0.03-0.03	0.02±0.00	0.01- 0.02	0.01±0.00	0.01-0.01	<0.0001
CRP mg/dL	0.06±0.05	0.01-0.18	0.06±0.05	0.01-0.15	0.05±0.06	0.01-0.21	0.6062

Data are presented as mean ± SD (n = 7 per group).

Statistical comparisons were performed using endpoint values obtained at day 60 of the experimental period.

Differences among groups were analyzed using one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's post hoc test.

Significance Levels: p < 0.05 (****): Statistically significant, p < 0.01 (**): Highly significant, p < 0.001 (***): Very highly significant, p < 0.0001 (****):

Extremely significant (NS: Not significant)

Table 2. Pearson correlation coefficients between metabolic, biochemical, and adipose tissue parameters in diet-induced obese rats.

361

362

	Weight		TBARS		WAT		BAT	
	r	p	r	p	r	p	r	p
Weight	-	-	0.72	0.0002	0.72	0.0002	-0.66	0.0010
WAT Weight	0.72	0.0002	0.71	0.0003	-	-	-0.77	<0.0001
BAT Weight	-0.66	0.0010	-0.83	<0.0001	-0.77	<0.0001	-	-
AST	0.57	0.0067	0.49	0.0256	0.44	0.05	-0.47	0.0334
ALT	0.63	0.0022	0.66	0.0011	0.45	0.04	-0.64	0.0017
Lipase	-0.61	0.0032	-0.76	<0.0001	-0.74	0.0001	0.89	<0.0001
Triglyceride	0.78	<0.0001	0.8038	<0.0001	0.85	<0.0001	-0.80	<0.0001
HDL	-0.47	0.03	-0.77	<0.0001	-0.63	0.0021	0.70	0.0005
LDL	0.30	0.1813	0.48	0.0262	0.47	0.0316	-0.39	0.0778
VLDL	0.78	<0.0001	0.80	<0.0001	0.85	<0.0001	-0.80	<0.0001
Total Cholesterol	0.68	0.0006	0.90	<0.0001	0.64	0.0018	-0.77	<0.0001
HOMA-IR	0.62	0.0025	0.83	<0.0001	0.67	0.0008	-0.82	<0.0001
TBARS	0.72	0.0002	-	-	0.71	0.0003	-0.83	<0.0001
Blood glucose	0.80	<0.0001	0.54	0.0118	0.54	0.0118	-0.61	0.003

363

Values represent Pearson correlation coefficients (r) and corresponding p-values (n = 21).

364

Statistically significant correlations ($p < 0.05$) indicate associations between metabolic and biochemical parameters.

365

Positive correlations indicate direct associations, whereas negative correlations indicate inverse associations.

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Correlation analyses reflect relationships between variables and do not imply causality.

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Significance levels: $p < 0.05$ (), $p < 0.01$ (), $p < 0.001$ (), $p < 0.0001$ (****).

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4. Discussion

The global rise in obesity continues to direct attention toward interventions that can influence metabolic regulation and gut microbiota–host interactions. Kombucha tea is a naturally fermented drink that has been investigated for potential metabolic relevance in diet-induced obesity models [29]. In the present study, we compared the metabolic effects of probiotic kombucha tea with those of its postbiotic-like cell-free filtrate in rats with diet-induced obesity. Overall, the postbiotic preparation was associated with broader and more consistent improvements across metabolic readouts than the probiotic form, including lipid parameters, insulin resistance indices, liver-related markers, brown adipose tissue (BAT) mass, and oxidative stress.

A key observation was that postbiotic supplementation produced a more pronounced improvement in the lipid profile compared with probiotic kombucha. This pattern aligns with reports on *Lactobacillus paragasseri* SBT2055, which has been shown to attenuate obesity-related metabolic alterations and reduce adiposity in experimental models [30]. In the context of kombucha fermentation, such improvements are plausibly linked to the bioactive metabolite fraction present in the cell-free filtrate, including organic acids.

The antimicrobial activity observed for the kombucha-derived postbiotic can be explained largely by its organic acid composition. Acetic and lactic acids are known to contribute to bacteriostatic effects through acidification and membrane-related mechanisms, and similar antimicrobial patterns have been reported for kombucha-derived preparations [31,32]. In line with the ISAPP consensus definition, postbiotics are bioactive preparations containing inanimate microorganisms and/or their components that confer a health benefit on the host, thereby enabling delivery of bioactivity without viable cells [33]. In the present study, seven major organic acids were detected, with acetic and lactic acids as dominant components, followed by gluconic, malic, citric, oxalic, and succinic acids. The combined action of these acids plausibly accounts for the transient bacteriostatic activity detected in our assays, consistent with prior reports [31,32]. In addition, Atik et al. reported that kombucha-derived preparations enriched in key acids can exhibit strong antibacterial activity, supporting the link between organic acid accumulation and antimicrobial potency [34].

The kombucha tea and its postbiotic filtrate also showed comparable total phenolic content and antioxidant activity. These values are consistent with ranges reported for kombucha-derived preparations in metabolomics-oriented and bioactivity-focused studies [32]. This agreement supports the reliability of the analytical profile and suggests that phenolic retention may coexist with organic acid enrichment in the postbiotic-like fraction.

Gut microbiota alterations are widely associated with obesity-related metabolic dysfunction, including shifts in community composition and functional capacity that relate to energy harvest and barrier integrity [35–37]. Consistent with this concept, germ-free models have demonstrated resistance to diet-induced obesity under certain conditions, emphasizing the contribution of microbiota-dependent mechanisms to host energy balance [38]. Within this framework, fermented products and their postbiotic fractions may influence metabolic endpoints through microbial metabolites that interact with host pathways.

A novel finding of the present study is the association between postbiotic supplementation and increased BAT mass in obese rats. Because direct thermogenic activity markers (e.g., UCP1 expression or energy expenditure) were not measured, this result should be interpreted as an anatomical/phenotypic change consistent with pathways related to thermogenic potential. Prior work has shown that prebiotic/postbiotic-related

metabolites can modulate browning and adaptive thermogenesis pathways, including UCP1-related signaling, often via AMPK-linked or broader metabolic signaling networks [39,40]. Moreover, Reynés et al. summarized that postbiotic metabolites, including organic acids, can contribute to thermogenesis through adrenergic and non-adrenergic mechanisms [40]. In this context, the presence of succinate in the postbiotic-like filtrate is noteworthy, as succinate has been shown to participate in mechanisms that promote adipose tissue thermogenesis in experimental systems [41]. These findings provide a plausible biological framework for why BAT-related differences may accompany the metabolic improvements observed.

The relatively high acetic acid concentration and the detection of succinic acid in the filtrate further support this framework, as both metabolites have been discussed as modulators of mitochondrial metabolism, lipid handling, and thermogenesis-related pathways in the postbiotic literature [40–42]. Specifically, broader reviews of postbiotic mechanisms highlight that organic acids and related metabolites can influence mitochondrial respiration and lipid oxidation processes, which may translate into systemic metabolic effects [42].

In addition to group-based comparisons, correlation and regression analyses provided further insight into the interrelationships among metabolic parameters. Body weight showed a strong inverse association with brown adipose tissue (BAT) mass and lipase activity, while being positively associated with white adiposity, lipid parameters, insulin resistance, and oxidative stress. These relationships support the interpretation that the reductions in body weight observed with postbiotic supplementation are closely linked to coordinated changes in adipose tissue distribution and lipid metabolism rather than isolated effects on single metabolic markers.

Notably, oxidative stress emerged as a central variable, displaying strong positive associations with triglycerides, total cholesterol, and HOMA-IR, alongside negative relationships with BAT mass and HDL. Regression analyses further identified oxidative stress and blood glucose as independent contributors to body weight variation, reinforcing the concept that redox imbalance and glycemic dysregulation are key drivers of obesity-related metabolic deterioration. Collectively, these findings strengthen the mechanistic coherence of the study by demonstrating that improvements in BAT-related parameters, lipid handling, and oxidative stress are tightly interconnected outcomes of postbiotic intervention. Although BAT mass did not emerge as an independent predictor in multivariate regression models, this likely reflects shared variance with closely related metabolic parameters rather than a lack of biological relevance.

Oxidative stress is a key contributor to obesity-related metabolic dysfunction. In the present study, postbiotic supplementation was associated with a clear reduction in TBARS, consistent with decreased lipid peroxidation. Similar antioxidant/oxidative stress-related improvements have been reported with postbiotic preparations in metabolic syndrome-oriented animal models [43]. While TBARS provides useful insight into lipid peroxidation, future studies incorporating additional enzymatic antioxidant markers would further strengthen mechanistic interpretation.

In contrast to the improvements observed in lipid handling, insulin resistance indices, liver-related markers, BAT mass, and TBARS, CRP did not differ significantly between groups. This finding differs from some reports suggesting anti-inflammatory effects of postbiotic preparations [44] and indicates that inflammatory readouts may be context-dependent, biomarker-specific, or require longer interventions and/or complementary inflammatory panels for clearer resolution.

Taken together, these results indicate that kombucha-derived postbiotics may act through multiple complementary mechanisms—dominated by an organic acid-rich bioactive fraction—potentially involving metabolic modulation, BAT-associated pathways, and antioxidant protection, thereby contributing to improvements in obesity-related metabolic disturbances.

5. Conclusions

This study demonstrates that a kombucha-derived postbiotic-like cell-free filtrate exerts broader and more consistent metabolic benefits than probiotic kombucha tea in a rat model of diet-induced obesity. Postbiotic supplementation was associated with favorable changes in body weight trajectory, adipose tissue distribution, lipid profile, liver-related markers, insulin resistance indices, and oxidative stress, whereas inflammatory status as assessed by CRP remained unchanged.

The observed metabolic improvements appear to be linked to coordinated alterations in lipid handling, oxidative balance, and brown adipose tissue-related parameters, likely mediated by the organic acid-rich bioactive fraction of the postbiotic preparation.

Despite limitations including sample size, absence of microbiota profiling, and lack of direct thermogenic activity measurements, these findings support the potential of kombucha-derived postbiotics as a promising dietary strategy for metabolic regulation in obesity. Future studies incorporating microbiota analysis, thermogenesis-related markers, histological evaluation, and translational designs are warranted.

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Abbreviations

The following abbreviations are used in this manuscript:

AST	Aspartate Aminotransferase
ALT	Alanine Aminotransferase
TBARS	Thiophene-Barbituric Acid Reactive Substances-Oxidative Stress
HOMA-IR	Homeostatic Model Assessment of Insulin Resistance
LDL	Low-Density Lipoprotein
CRP	C-Reactive Protein
WHO	World Health Organisation
NAHS	Non-Alcoholic Hepatic Steatosis
TNF- α	Tumour Necrosis Factor-A
IL-6	Interleukin-6
NF- κ B	Nuclear Factor Kappa B (NF-Kb)
JNK	C-Jun N-Terminal Kinase
ALP	Alkaline Phosphatase

GGT	Gamma-Glutamyl Transferase
LDH	Lactate Dehydrogenase
SCOBY	Symbiotic Culture of Bacteria and Yeast
PTFE	Polytetrafluoroethylene
MRS	Man Rogosa Sharpe
LAB	Lactic Acid Bacteria
DPPH	2,2-Diphenyl-1-Picrylhydrazyl
MIC	Minimum Inhibitory Concentration
ATCC	American Type Culture Collection
MHB	Mueller–Hinton Broth
HFD	High-Fat Diet
HDL	High Density Lipoprotein
MDA	Malondialdehyde
WAT	White Adipose Tissue
BAT	Brown Adipose Tissue
VLDL	Very-Low-Density Lipoprotein
\bar{X}	Average
SD	Standard Deviation
p	Probability
r	Correlation
ISAPP	International Scientific Association For Probiotic And Prebiotics
UCP1	Uncoupling Protein 1
AMPK	Adenosine Monophosphate Activated Protein Kinase

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